

Entrepreneurs and Entrepreneurship in Gaza Strip between Reality and Ambition

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Abstract: The study aimed to identify entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in Gaza Strip. The researchers used the analytical descriptive approach to achieve the objectives of the study. The study community consists of 92 of the pilot projects benefiting from the three incubators in Gaza Strip (the Palestinian Information Technology Incubator, the Technology Incubator, the Business Incubator and Technology). The researchers used the comprehensive inventory method. To answer the study questions and to examine their hypotheses, the arithmetical averages, the standard deviation, the T test and the analysis of the mono-variance were used followed by a quiz test. The problem of the study in the main question: What is the reality of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in Gaza Strip. The study found a number of results, the most important of which are: Men are more oriented towards entrepreneurship than females. And that scientific qualification does not affect entrepreneurship. And many are looking for entrepreneurs who do not have practical experience in the labor market, but are subject to training courses through the business incubator. Based on the findings, the researchers recommend stimulating male entrepreneurship and promoting it in females. And to design training programs to refine entrepreneurial skills. And the need to add the course of entrepreneurship in the majority of university disciplines.

Keywords: Entrepreneurs, Entrepreneurship, Gaza Strip, Palestine

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is essential for economic progress. The development of countries is measured by the size of entrepreneurship applied, and the ability to develop and innovate in these businesses. In the Arab world, there is a large percentage of educated minds, but we suffer from a lack of leadership to develop the country's economy. The Arab world is suffering from the absence of economic integration despite the availability of resources. On the contrary, Japan lacks the resources of the most economically advanced nations in the world.

Entrepreneurship is an important topic in the world today, because it drives economic growth significantly through the means, tools and resources available in the economy itself. The concept of entrepreneurship varies according to several determinants such as: culture, society, economics, and associated qualities of distinctive members of society, because it converges with several other trends, and thus begins to confuse them. Entrepreneurship in our general concept leads to the start of a private enterprise, although this is one view of entrepreneurship, or one of the goals they aspire to achieve (Hamed and Rashid, 2007), while business incubators are important mechanisms in the development of entrepreneurship, where Projects are born from birth as an idea to the implementation stage Actual. These incubators create the right conditions for start-ups to ensure their

continuity, and support for new project ideas at all levels during the incubation period (Abdullah, et al., 2014).

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Young people are one of the most important resources that all institutions of society must invest in order to achieve integrated and sustainable development (Amayreh, 2008), (Al Shobaki & Abu-Naser, 2017). Every person at Harvard invents something, and Harvard students believe that creating / inventing work is better than looking for work (Fincher, 2010).

Young people should be guided to create their own jobs, through entrepreneurship that has achieved remarkable success and development in developed countries. For example, Brazil has supported entrepreneurship to reduce unemployment, succeeding in reducing the rate from (12.3%) in 2004 to (8.1%) in 2010, by supporting the orientation of entrepreneurship (Al-Shamshiri and Al-Mubairik, 2010).

The study (Qunlian, 2011) highlighted the importance of encouraging university graduates to entrepreneurship to create more jobs. Entrepreneurship has become a key strategy for dealing with the employment problems of the Chinese government. (Al-Houli and Al-Houli, 2012) reported that entrepreneurship still needed further academic studies.

The researchers interviewed the director of the Faten Foundation with one of its employees. They said that the institution wanted to lend to young people, but young people did not dare to borrow because they had nothing to underwrite and fear of being unable to pay. On the reality of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurs in Gaza Strip, and in the light of previous data, the research problem was formulated in the form of the following main question:

Q1:- What is the reality of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship in Gaza Strip?

3. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The importance of this study is that it is looking at a modern subject and is aimed at countries to develop their country and improve the economic situation and promote it through leadership.

1. This research may enrich the scientific side of the researchers, which is reflected positively on both the professional and the scientific side.
2. This study is part of efforts to address the widespread unemployment among Palestinian youth, who constitute a very large and important segment of Palestinian human resources.

4. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

In light of the search problem, the basic objectives of the research can be defined as follows:

1. Identify the concept and reality of entrepreneurship and its importance to society.
2. Identify the demographic variables that affect the start of entrepreneurship.
3. Identify differences in respondents' responses to entrepreneurship due to personal variables

5. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The main hypothesis states that: **H₀**: There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the respondents' responses to entrepreneurship according to

personal variables (age, gender, name of business incubator, educational qualification, years of experience in entrepreneurial work).

6. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Firstly- Entrepreneurship

Young people have enormous mental and physical skills and capacities, and they are the most ambitious and receptive to change. This underscores the importance and vitality of their role in social and economic development through entrepreneurship, flexible microenterprises and rapid response to market changes, creating opportunities Action, and integration into the wheel of sustainable development.

Entrepreneurship is originally a French word for a person who initiates or initiates a business. The famous French economist and businessman Jean-Baptiste, the owner of the economic law called the Sai Law, first used the term in 1800 in the same sense. The caravan was advancing and preceded by the convoys to determine the location of its residence, where leadership represents the ability and initiative to carry out a work, or the establishment of a new facility.

Early economists recognized the importance of entrepreneurship for the growth of the economy. They considered entrepreneurs as captains of industry, growth leaders, and focused on their skills in organizing and conducting successful business. They emphasized that the more entrepreneurs in an economy, the more it contributed to the growth of the economy (Barnouti, 2008), (Al Shobaki et al., 2018).

Entrepreneurship Concept:

Although entrepreneurship is an ancient term throughout the ages, and the subject has been the subject of much research and writing, there is no definite definition of entrepreneurship. (BCHINI, 2014) In this paper, the researchers will discuss some of the concepts of leadership as shown in Table (1):

Table 1: Concept of Entrepreneurship

No.	Author	Concept
1.	(Sethi, 2005)	Entrepreneurship is a dynamic, risky process involving a combination of capital, technology and human skill, and is applicable in all businesses, regardless of size and economic or service orientation.
2.	(Abderrahim, 2013)	It is the process of creating value by investing opportunity through unique resources.
3.	(Ersin and zçeli, 2013)	Creating economic value through the development of new products, services, processes, or markets, described by global leadership observers as an attempt to start a new business through the development of business or the creation of a new business by an individual or a group of individuals.
4.	(Durukan, 2006)	Entrepreneur is the person who sees the demand gap in the market.
5.	(Aramex, 2013)	An entrepreneur is a person who has the ability to take risks and has the courage to put plans into action, where many people have ideas, but do not begin to implement.
6.	(Ersin and Özçelik, 2013)	An entrepreneur is an energetic person who develops his / her work extensively over a short period of time.

7.	(Abdullah, et al., 2014)	<p>An entrepreneur is someone who takes the full risk to the business he runs, An entrepreneur is planning, creating or allocating the necessary elements of production from capital and land, hiring and combining workers from his or her family members, managing them to produce and market goods or services, and taking financial and legal risks to the ownership and management of the project, which either generates profits or incurs losses as a result of its activity. Economic.</p>
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Source: Researchers prepared in light of their reading of the literature

Procedural definition of researchers:

Researchers have identified entrepreneurship as a process by someone with special qualities such as creativity, excellence, and risk-taking.

Through the figure below, we note that the entrepreneurial idea arises through the entrepreneur's perception of a noticeable or unnoticeable gap in consumer needs, and wants to satisfy it through certain services or products.

Figure 1: generation of entrepreneurial ideas

Source: Inventory by researchers 2019

The importance of leadership:

In their economy and development, superpowers rely on entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship, as they play an important role in the state's economy. The entry of entrepreneurs and exit from the market and to help in the redistribution of wealth to new allocations and more effective, and when stationed move at a geographic point, the

productivity generated by the entry of entrepreneurs and exit may turn into a competitive advantage for that region, high rates of growth in the local economy. Entrepreneurs are setting up new enterprises, which in turn generate jobs, increase competition, and may increase productivity through technological change, and therefore, RIAD, and RIAD (Hamed and Rashid, 2007).

Table 2: Benefits of Entrepreneurship

Benefits of Entrepreneurship	
A study of (Al-Shamshiri and Al-Mubairik, 2010)	A study of (Alvijan, 2010)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Independence - Opportunities for excellence - An opportunity to achieve maximum ambitions - Opportunity to make profits - Opportunity to contribute to society - Create other jobs for others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating wealth - Improve national income. - Activating production factors. - Encourage innovation. - Change the culture of society by changing the business culture. - Creating new business and economic activities that create jobs and create new markets.

Source: Inventory by researchers based on previous literature

Many researchers have tried to identify the entrepreneur, and to do many tests to know the characteristics of the entrepreneurial personality, and the details of the entrepreneurial personality are still not subject to be placed in a single mold, different and different thinking and different, different and different thinking, and different Religious.

Obstacles to Entrepreneurship

Each one of us has concerns, it may be fear of something that will not be realized, for example, you think that your request for funding will be rejected, or that the idea of turning your site into a large company will not be realized. At the root of all this fear lies failure. Therefore, if you fear failure and are not prepared to deal with it, you will lose your ability to overcome risks, and if you lose your ability to overcome risks, you will not get real results, which ends in stagnation.

(Abu Naser et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2018), and the Palestinian Business Forum, 2014, presented some of the obstacles facing the Palestinian entrepreneur on the ground, namely: -

1. Policy constraints (Zionist occupation)
2. Constraints in management
3. Obstacles to access to technology
4. Constraints to poor infrastructure
5. Obstacles to obtaining raw materials
6. Constraints in financing

There are several obstacles facing entrepreneurs, which are the funding, needed to establish the project, the time to start implementing it, and the difficulty in obtaining raw materials, especially the people of Gaza Strip. The sector has been facing a siege for several consecutive years. Entrepreneurs, and the risk posed by the leader is one of the obstacles, his idea may not be accepted in the market.

Jane Holden explained in her Principles of Entrepreneurship (2007) that most economists today agreed that entrepreneurship is necessary to stimulate economic growth and secure employment in all societies. In the developing world, successful small businesses are the primary drivers of job creation, income development and poverty reduction. The form of a government support strategy for business initiative is therefore crucial to economic development.

Second- Business Incubators

Entrepreneurship contributes to creating jobs, increasing income, improving the economic situation, and must have a good structure to help them start, grow, and grow. But what we see on the ground is that entrepreneurial projects face obstacles to success. Here comes the role of business incubators which aims to eliminate these obstacles by providing several services for start-ups such as: finance and advisory services, and encourage innovation through several training programs and others.

Business incubators have become one of the important and evolving mechanisms in the world today, which can effectively contribute to the elimination of economic and

social problems to address small and medium-sized enterprises in all countries of the world (Samai, 2010).

Business Incubator Concept:

There are several definitions for business incubators. Examples include:

Known (Al-Azzam and Musa, 2010) as an integrated system of activities are managed in accordance with the specialized administrative structures carrying visions backed by the expertise of practical and scientific strategy, and provide adequate and equipped spaces needed to start the pilot joint ventures potential as incubators provide administrative services, as well as technical support services Channels of communication in the business community, to increase the chances of success and reduce the risk of Shell pilot projects have Incubated.

(Samai, 2010) That it is a place that serves as an environment for a particular thing, regardless of its type, the incubator embraces him, cares for him, provides him with the necessary protection from any risks to him and provides him with continuous energy for the purpose of maintenance.

(Ghayat and Buqumum, 2009) defined it as an integrated environment of facilities and mechanisms supporting entrepreneurs in the initiation, management, development and development of economic institutions, and sponsorship for a limited period of not more than three years to ensure greater opportunities for success, and reduce the size of risks, and the probability of failure Encountered by creating a legal entity established for this purpose with the necessary possibilities and networking.

(Khalil and Hanaa, 2006) It is one of the mechanisms adopted to support small start-up enterprises. It is a stand-alone institution with a legal personality. It provides a range of services and facilities for small enterprises to overcome the burdens of the start-up stage. The business incubator may be a private, mixed, or state-owned enterprise, and the latter gives it stronger support.

Origin of incubators:

The incubators date back to the first project that was set up in the manufacturing center known as (Batavia) in the state of New York, USA, in (1959) when a family converted the headquarters of the company that stopped working to a business center whose units are rented to individuals who want to set up a project with Provide advice and advice to them. This idea was very successful, and this idea later turned into what is known as incubator, and at the end of (1997) the number of incubators in the United States (550) incubators (Al-Shabrawy, 2005).

Importance of business incubators

The King Abdulaziz University (2005) study emphasized the leading role of incubation institutions in the economic development and growth of the communities they serve, and the prosperity of programs in the major cities and suburbs as well as rural communities, where the programs succeeded in the establishment of many different small companies that opened new opportunities for work and generate revenue Depends on them in their areas.

Business Incubator Success Conditions:

Business incubators, like any administrative entity that requires success, provide a set of conditions and may be subject to obstacles that stand in the way of achieving the goals.

Conditions for Success of Business Incubators (Abdul Raziq, 2014)

- Awareness of entrepreneurs and small business owners about the benefits that incubators will provide.
- Studies should be carried out before any project can be initiated and its applicability can be noted.
- Develop and develop legislation and regulations governing public and private sector cooperation.
- Establishing cooperative relations between the parties concerned.
- Continuous evaluation and improvement.

Services provided by business incubators

Business incubators provide services in a variety of different fields, including all aspects that help the success of the pilot project. Table 3 shows the services provided by business incubators.

Table 3: Services provided by incubators

(Rihanna and Bonwalah, 2011)	(Social Fund for Development, 2011)
- Administrative services	- Technical services
- Secretarial services	- Marketing services
- Financing Services	- Accounting Services
- Specialized services (consulting, marketing)	- Administrative Services

Source: Inventory by researchers after reviewing the above sources

Business Incubator types:

Figure 2: types of incubators

Source: Inventory by researchers

In this example, there are incubators that seek to support the pioneering ideas related to the field of technology, and others that support the pioneering ideas in the field of agriculture, and we find some incubators that seek to achieve Profit by sharing ownership of projects.

Incubators available in Gaza Strip

1. Business and Technology Incubator at the Islamic University:

The incubator for business and technology is a new unit established by the Islamic University with the support of InfoDev for the first stage and the Quality Development Fund for the second phase. It was founded in 2012. The incubator aims to support the development of small economic activities related to the technology sector. Providing professional business services to Palestinian entrepreneurs who have mature ideas for unique and innovative products in technology and are estimated to have a strong potential market.

Mission Incubator Business and Technology

Design, development, implementation and marketing of innovative initiatives in the IT sector that will support the development of high-potential entrepreneurial ventures by providing them with a full suite of world-class business development services that will play a role in promoting and promoting the commercialization of ideas , Improve the development and growth of effective enterprises.

2. ICT Incubator (BCTI)

Information and Communication Technology Incubator Palestine (PCTI), an independent Palestinian organization based in Ramallah, has a branch in Gaza that was built to stimulate and support the growth of ICT in Palestine. It aims to develop small, medium and small (and small and medium) enterprises in order to create new jobs and improve the economic situation in Palestine.

3. Technology Incubator at the University College of Applied Sciences

The Technological Incubator is a new unit established at the University College of Applied Sciences, established in 2013 with the support of the Economic Recovery Project in Gaza Strip, implemented in partnership with Oxfam and funded by the Danish Agency for International Development (DANIDA). The incubator aims to support entrepreneurs and IT leaders through Develop their creative ideas and reflect them on the ground.

The role of the technological incubator

The technological incubator seeks to provide the environment for the development of innovative ideas in the field of information technology and transform them into products that meet the needs of society.

The importance of entrepreneurship as a solution to the problem of rising unemployment in Gaza Strip derives from the above. The role of business incubators is to provide an appropriate environment for the seeds of these projects so that they grow properly and help their success.

7. LITERATURE REVIEW

- The Study of (Abu Qarn, 2015) aimed to identify the reality of entrepreneurship in Palestinian universities through a comparative study between the Deanship of Community Service and Continuing Education at the Islamic University and the Center for Continuing Education at Al-Azhar University. The sample of the study consisted of 160 students from the Islamic University and Al-Azhar University. The results of the study showed that there is an average role for creativity, innovation, calculated risk, autonomy, competitiveness and entrepreneurial culture on the pioneering orientation in the continuing education in the Islamic University, while it shows that there is little role for the above mentioned areas on the pioneering direction in the continuing education in Al-Azhar University. It recommended that the Department of Continuing Education at Al-Azhar University work to develop the Center for Continuing Education and raise the level of entrepreneurship, and the need for continuing education at the Islamic University to better and more support the research and development projects to support innovation and creativity and provide the environment and supporting physical and information infrastructure, and to seek funding and training on Entrepreneurship and consulting services in marketing and other fields, in both universities.
- The Study of (Eleodinmuo and Priscillia, 2015) aimed at analyzing the socio-economic characteristics of the performance of the workforce in small and medium enterprises, to learn about the perception of entrepreneurship policies to find SMEs and to know the problem that prevents the growth of small and medium enterprises. Aba, Apia State, Nigeria. Among the findings of the study, APA's leadership policies such as education, access to finance and SME development are facing poor implementation. There were several

recommendations, the most important of which is to consider government measures to finance entrepreneurs and to facilitate access to them; Reassess most government policies that make the business environment in SMEs an appropriate one. Orienting the objective and policies of government projects for small enterprises towards sustainability and providing the infrastructure for entrepreneurship.

- The Study of (Støren, 2014) aimed at exposing the percentage of graduates of higher education in Norway who conducted various forms of entrepreneurship education and the inclusiveness of entrepreneurship education. Higher Entrepreneurship in Norway. One of the main findings of the study is that the proportion of self-employed entrepreneurs is very low, not higher than other graduates. The results suggest that entrepreneurship graduates are somewhat more interested in setting up their own companies in the future, but this tendency is much lower than what exists in other European studies. She also found that entrepreneurship education contributes to increasing entrepreneurial skills in general. One of the most important recommendations of the study is also to focus on graduating students with creative skills, and make entrepreneurship a comprehensive curriculum and not specific to specific disciplines.
- The Study of (Ramadan, 2012), which aimed to study the variables forming theories associated with the initiation of entrepreneurial work;. The most important finding is that the percentage of students who prefer to work for their own account is higher than those who prefer to work with others, whether public or private sector. The results of the study show that there are differences in the intention of the student towards entrepreneurship, due to the gender variable, and the fact that one or both parents have entrepreneurial work. One of the most important recommendations proposed by the study is to direct training programs at the community and family level, to enhance the student's self-confidence through the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills to raise the likelihood of doing business.
- The Study of (Mohammed and Abdul Karim, 2011), which aimed to diagnose the reality of small and medium entrepreneurship in the Palestinian economy through the diagnosis of the most prominent obstacles in front of them, and the development of possible proposals aimed at overcoming these obstacles, and the study adopted descriptive analytical research method through researchers to look at Many secondary sources. The most important findings of the study are that the obstacles facing Palestinian entrepreneurship are not applying modern administrative methods, relying on inherited family experiences, using untrained and qualified manpower, and old technological methods. The existence of highly competitive projects by Israeli goods and cheap foreign goods that flood the Palestinian

market, which exposes the Palestinian consumer to less than the cost of the domestic product, and the deteriorating political and economic conditions in the Palestinian territories not only leads to the absence of clear economic plans, but also weakens the future vision. Among entrepreneurs, and blocking the prospects for these projects. The study recommends increasing the government role and activating it in supporting small projects, providing infrastructure requirements for the work of entrepreneurial projects, and spreading the culture of entrepreneurship in Palestinian society through higher education institutions.

- The Study of (Dehleaz, 2009) aimed at identifying the role of business incubators in developing the skills of entrepreneurs and encouraging the establishment of small businesses in Gaza Strip. The study sample consists of students at the Islamic University of Gaza who are studying at the last level of the bachelor's degree in the faculties of engineering, commerce and information technology in various disciplines in those faculties. Students are classified into two categories: Entrepreneurial and Non-Entrepreneurial. The most important findings are: The majority of entrepreneurial students are in the Faculty of Engineering and Business Administration. Funding is the most important requirement of business incubation and success in business incubators. The study did not show statistically significant differences between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs. While there are differences between the two groups in business-related skills, the data showed that two-thirds of the entrepreneurial students were male. It also showed a correlation between the type of job held by the father and the pioneering tendencies among students; while there is no correlation between these tendencies and the educational level of parents. The study recommended the need for a comprehensive national plan to promote the small business sector and business incubators and to achieve cooperation between academic institutions, the private sector, industry and official government agencies. Universities graduate entrepreneurs and are interested in scientific research, scientific development laboratories, and the private sector has the financial potential and governments concerned to achieve economic prosperity and reduce unemployment.

- The Study of (Hamed and Rashid, 2007) aimed to address the issue of entrepreneurship among young people through focusing on two phases. The study was applied to a sample of higher education students, small business owners, those from the age group (19-29), and related institutions. One of the most important findings is that the youth entrepreneurship rate in the economy did not exceed 14.2%, as young people prefer to look for job opportunities with others for a number of reasons, where the stages of higher education still focus only on the preparation of students, or students. They do not focus on preparing them for entrepreneurship. There is also a lack of incubators that embrace entrepreneurial and entrepreneurial ideas, and do not focus on preparing them for entrepreneurship. Incubators. And the difficulty of finding a source of capital for the project is the main reason to impede the establishment of pioneering work, as the commercial banks and microfinance institutions do not give special Hrutaó Balryadjien or young people, and treat them like any other segment, so asking them guarantees Kalomlak mortgaged. The study recommended encouraging youth entrepreneurship in education, encouraging banks and financial policy makers to allocate programs to finance youth entrepreneurship, amending the law to encourage investment, and incorporating the concept of learning by experience.

8. METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES OF THE STUDY

First: The Study Method

The study relied on the descriptive analytical method

Second: Study community and data collection method

The study community is represented in the pilot projects benefiting from business incubators in Gaza Strip, namely the Palestinian Information and Technology Incubator, Incubator of Business and Technology, Incubator of the University College of Applied Sciences. The researchers used a comprehensive method of collecting data from pilot projects benefiting from incubators, Represent the study community to ensure representation of all groups. Table (4) shows the number of projects in business incubators in Gaza Strip, where the questionnaire was distributed to one item per project.

Table 4: Distribution of the study population by business incubators

No.	Business Incubator	Number of projects	Number of questionnaires retrieved	Recovery ratio
1.	Palestinian Information and Technology Incubator	27	24	89%
2.	Business Incubator Technology	55	49	89%
3.	University College of Applied Sciences	10	9	90%
	Total	92	82	89%

After the completion of the data collection process and the retrieval of the questionnaires distributed, (82) valid answers were retrieved out of (92) distributed questionnaire. It is

noted from the above table that the rate of recovery in each incubator of information and technology Palestinian

incubator business and technology in the Islamic University amounted to (89%).

It also reached (90%) of the University College of Applied Sciences, and thus the proportion of recovery questionnaires from the total questionnaires distributed (89%), and this percentage is very excellent, and representative of the study community, and reliable in completing the study procedures, and some believe that the percentage of recovery that increase 40% or 50% is acceptable and reliable, and according to his findings (Sekaran, 2000) a minimum recovery rate of 30% is suitable for research purposes.

Data analysis and interpretation of results

The researchers review the data analysis and test the hypotheses of the study by answering the study questions and reviewing the main results of the questionnaire, which were reached through the analytical statistical procedures. The respondents were also described according to the personal data. Statistical analyzes of the data collected from the questionnaire the study, related to the paragraphs, dimensions, and axes of the study. The SPSS program was used to obtain the results of the study presented and analyzed.

The main hypothesis:

Ho: There are statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the respondents' responses to entrepreneurship according to personal variables (age, gender, name of business incubator, educational qualification, years of experience in entrepreneurial work).

To validate this hypothesis, the T test was used in the cases of the two independent samples to test the differences due to the sex variable and the scientific qualification, while the One Way ANOVA was used to test the differences attributed to other variables consisting of more than two groups, the hypothesis test follows both individual variables.

▪ **For the age variable.**

The One Way ANOVA test was used to test the nihilistic hypothesis (Ho) which assumes that there are no statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the age variable, versus the alternative hypothesis (H1) which

Table 6: Test results (T) to verify differences in entrepreneurship according to gender variable

Gender	SMA	Relative Weight%	Standard Deviation	T-test	Sig
Male	3.79	76%	0.37	-0.29	0.005
Female	4.04	81%	0.33		

It is noted from the previous table that the value of the calculated significance of the test (Sig = 0.005) to verify the existence of a fundamental difference was less than the level of 0.05, which means the rejection of the nihilistic hypothesis, and the conclusion of the alternative hypothesis that there are statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the gender variable, and those differences were In favor of females by (0.25) degree. The relative weight of male responses to entrepreneurship as a whole was 76% and 81% for females.

Therefore, we conclude that the hypothesis of the study, which assumes that there are statistically significant

assumes that there are statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the variable Age, and table 5 below shows the test result.

Table 5: ANOVA test results to verify differences in entrepreneurship according to age variable

Age	SMA	Relative Weight%	Standard Deviation	F-test	Sig
Less than 22 years	3.92	78%	0.43	0.868	0.424
26 to 30 years old	3.87	77%	0.26		
More than 30 years	3.76	75%	0.45		

It is clear from Table (5) above that the value of the calculated test significance (Sig = 0.424) to verify the existence of significant differences was greater than the level of significance 0.05. The relative weight of respondents by age ranged from 75% for those over 30 years of age, and 78% for those aged under 22 to under 26. It should be noted here that the categories (less than 22 years) and (22 to less than 26 years) have been merged because the number of views in the first category is low.

Consequently, we conclude that the hypothesis that "there are statistically significant differences in entrepreneurship due to age variability" is incorrect.

Researchers attribute this to the fact that it is personal entrepreneurial qualities that influence entrepreneurship, regardless of age.

▪ **For the gender variable.**

Using the independent samples t-test, the null hypothesis (Ho), which assumes no statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the sex variable, was tested against the alternative hypothesis (H1) which assumed the existence of statistically significant differences about the entrepreneurship attributed to the sex variable. Table 6 below shows the test result.

differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the gender variable, is correct. This hypothesis is consistent with the study (Ramadan, 2012) where the previous study showed that there are differences in the intention of the student towards the trend of entrepreneurship due to the gender variable.

Researchers attribute this to the fact that males are looking for job stability, regardless of females who are more motivated to take risks because of their lack of responsibility.

▪ **For the business incubator name variable.**

The One Way ANOVA test was used to test the nihilistic hypothesis (Ho) which assumes that there are no statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the business incubator name variable, versus the alternative hypothesis (H1) which assumes statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship. Attributed to the business incubator name variable, Table 7 below shows the test result.

Table 7: ANOVA test results to verify the differences in entrepreneurship according to the name of the business incubator

Business Incubator Name	SMA	Relative Weight%	Standard Deviation	F-test	Sig
Palestinian Business and Technology Incubator	3.86	77%	0.33	0.848	0.432
Islamic University	3.90	78%	0.41		
University College of Applied Sciences	3.73	77%	0.33		

It is clear from table (7) above that the value of the calculated test significance (Sig = 0.432) to verify the existence of significant differences was greater than the level of significance 0.05 and this means acceptance of the null hypothesis which assumes that there are no statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the variable name of the business incubator. The relative weight of respondents according to the name of the business incubator ranged between 77% for the Palestinian Business Incubator and the Palestinian University College of Applied Sciences, and 78% for the Islamic University.

Consequently, we conclude that the hypothesis that "there are statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship due to the name of the business incubator" is incorrect.

The researchers attribute this to the incubation of all incubators in the goal of supporting entrepreneurship and providing a suitable environment for entrepreneurship to succeed.

▪ **For the qualification variable.**

Using the independent samples t-test, the null hypothesis (Ho) which assumes that there are no statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributable to the qualification variable was tested against the alternative hypothesis (H1) which assumed statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the variable. Qualification, table (8) below shows the test result.

Table 8: results of the test (T) to verify the differences in entrepreneurship according to the variable of educational qualification

Qualification	SMA	Relative Weight%	Standard Deviation	T-test	Sig
High School and Under and Bachelor	3.87	77%	0.36	-0.338	0.736
Postgraduate	3.90	78%	0.46		

It is noted from the previous table that the value of the calculated significance of the test (Sig = 0.736) to verify the existence of a significant difference was greater than the level of 0.05, which means acceptance of the nihilistic hypothesis, which assumes that there are no statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed to the qualification variable. The relative weight of the respondents with a bachelor's degree and below on entrepreneurship as a whole was 77% and 78% for those with a postgraduate degree. It should be noted that the categories (secondary and lower) and (Bachelor) have been merged because of the low number of views in the first category.

Consequently, we conclude that the hypothesis of the study, which assumes that "there are statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributable to the qualification variable" is incorrect.

The researchers attribute this to the link between leadership and factors of personal qualities and not scientific, and these qualities can be enhanced by the person in several different ways, such as training programs and management game.

▪ **For variable years' experience in entrepreneurial work.**

The One Way ANOVA test was used to test the nihilistic hypothesis (Ho) which assumes that there are no statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributable to years of experience variable, versus the alternative hypothesis (H1) which assumes statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship attributed for variable years of experience, Table 9 below shows the test result.

Table 9: ANOVA test results to verify the differences in entrepreneurship according to the variable of years of experience

Years of Experience	SMA	Relative Weight%	Standard Deviation	F-test	Sig
Less than one year	3.96	79%	0.40	1.140	0.325
From 1 year to less than 3 years	3.79	76%	0.29		
3years and over	3.89	78%	0.42		

It is clear from table (9) above that the value of the calculated significance of the test (Sig = 0.325) to verify the existence of significant differences was greater than the level of significance 0.05. We also note that the relative weight of the responses of individuals by years of experience ranged between 76% for those years of experience from one year to less than 3 years, and 79% for those years of experience less than one year. It should be noted here that the two categories (from 3 years less than 5 years) and (5 years and above) were merged because of the low number of views in the second category.

Consequently, we conclude that the hypothesis that "there are statistically significant differences on entrepreneurship due to variable years of experience" is incorrect.

Researchers attribute this because entrepreneurial ideas have been followed by a hobby or skills followed by a study of market needs.

9. RESULTS

After examining the analysis of the results and testing hypotheses, the study showed the following:

- The majority of the age groups heading towards entrepreneurship are 22-30 years old. The researchers attribute this ratio to the political situation in Gaza Strip, in addition to the division that led to the low employment rate in the government departments of this generation and the inability of the current government in Gaza to pay salaries due to political and economic reasons.
- Male attitudes towards entrepreneurship are much higher than females, and researchers attribute this to the responsibility and requirements placed upon them. Entrepreneurship is a source of income for them.
- Most business leaders are IT professionals and engineers, and researchers attribute this to the interest of business incubators in ICT-related entrepreneurship.

10. RECOMMENDATIONS

- To stimulate entrepreneurship in the gums and to promote them in females
- Work on designing training programs to refine entrepreneurial skills
- Add the course of entrepreneurship in the majority of university majors

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